

DOCUMENT REQUISITES LOCATION AND HISTORY OF FORMATION

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Abstract. This in the article document requirements location and history of formation about word goes. In the article reasonable idea and considerations brought passed.

Key words: official style, documents, cultural life, economic relationship.

РЕКВИЗИТЫ ДОКУМЕНТА МЕСТОПОЛОЖЕНИЕ И ИСТОРИЯ
ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. Это в статье требования документа местоположение и история формирования о слове идет. В статье разумная идея и соображения привели прошли.

Ключевые слова: официальный стиль, документы, культурная жизнь, экономические отношения.

The history of the formation of official style documents dates back to ancient times. The socio-political processes, cultural life, economic relations that took place in the past, first of all, enriched the lexical layer and were reflected in documents. In turn, the historical process plays a special role in the formation and current development of official style .

Documents have developed their own characteristics and, one might say, style. That is, the style of documents, which is now called the official style, has also gone through certain stages of development before reaching its current appearance and form. First of all, we would like to talk about the structure of documents. M. Kholbakov's treatise "Correspondence of Amir Temur with the Kings of Europe" contains four letters written by the great Amir Temur to the viceroy of the Byzantine emperor Manuel II Paleolog, John Paleolog, King Henry III of Castile, and King Charles IV of France, and translated copies of the letter written by Amir Temur's son Mironshah Mirzo to the kings of France and England. The treatise also contains translated copies of the replies sent by the French king Charles IV and the English king Henry IV to the great Amir Temur . [2] Although the letters are in a translated version, we used them as a source in our research to study the text structure.

In these letters, first of all, the author and the person to whom the letter was written are indicated, then the text and date, in some letters, where it was written, and the seal are given. Q.Sh. Omonov's observations show that in documents of the 14th-15th centuries, the introduction consists of three parts: praise, title, and address. [3;50.] "In documents in Uyghur script, there is no dedication (praise) to God. In Arabic script, there is." [3;48] The introductory part of the scholarly state documents indicates who granted the privilege, which shows that it was considered

a title in the medieval Muslim East . [3;50] The first lines in the documents, which begin with the words “We are Amir Temur Ko'ragon so'zim”, “Sultan Umarshaykh Bahadur so'zum”, “Temur Kutlug' so'zum”, can be considered examples of this part.[2;20-21.] In our opinion, the title is a part indicating the lineage and rank of the person who wrote the document. Because not all documents grant privileges. The date and seal are also considered the main parts of the documents.

At the end of each document, the date of its writing is necessarily indicated. “It was written on the first day of the month of Muharram 805 AH (August 1, 1402 AH)”.[2;21.] Some documents indicate the date and place where it was written. “The history was completed on the sixth day of the month of Shaban in the year eight hundred and forty-six, in Mujawaran, on the banks of the Uzu River” (1397) [4;34.], as in “The seal of the house was completed on the twenty-eighth of the month of Shawwal in Andagan.” [4;35]

The seal indicated the official force of the document. For this reason , researchers pay special attention to it when studying documents. For example, “lines 3-5 are written inward from the rest, and in front of them is the khan's seal written in Arabic script in the form of a square.” [4;34.] The next two lines continue from one edge of the page, and in front of them is a circular seal in the middle of the page. [4;36.] Therefore, the shape of the seals, which were the structural part of the documents and ensured their officiality, was already in the form of a triangle and a square.

Q.Sh. Omonov, who studied the State documents granting the right of privilege in the Uyghur script of the 11th-15th centuries , shows that the style of documents is unique in terms of word composition and selection of lexical units, that is, in official texts only lexical units characteristic of the style of documents are used, and not all units of the general Turkic lexical structure are used. He emphasizes that the style of documents does not contain units characteristic of works of art and oral speech, and that artistic means of depiction are not used to figuratively express life events and describe human spiritual experiences and feelings. [3;26.] “The reason why not all general Turkic lexical units of that period are used in the style of official texts is explained, first of all, by the “formality” required by the official literary language characteristic of the style of documents.” [3;28.]

Omonov specifically focuses on the word "so'zum" in his observations. He emphasizes that this word, in the meaning of "my word", has nothing to do with the formal style, but rather acquires a special meaning, such as "order, decree", ensuring the formality of documents.[3;52.]

Historian Usmanov expresses the following opinion: “It is known that all khan inscriptions, as a rule, begin with the word “... khan”. Research shows that “... khan’s word is characteristic not of inscriptions, but only of inscriptions”. However, we would like to mention that Amir Temur’s second letter to the French king Charles VI begins with the words “Who are we, Amir

Temur Ko'ragon" [2;21.] and the letter of Amir Temur's son Mironshah Mirzo to the kings of France and England begins with the words "Who are we, Mironshah Ko'ragon". [2;23.] Of course, this is a translation of the originals, but when comparing the letters with their Latin versions, we also witnessed the form "Temur Ruranan Sosumus" [2;29.], "Miranxa Curanan Sosumus" [2;31.] It is important to note that "Our Word" begins with capital letters and is given without any changes. Undoubtedly, this is also an achievement of the official style of the Turkic language (although it was not called that at that time). In order to further substantiate our opinion, we paid attention to the location of the sentences in the letters reflecting the diplomatic relations of the great Amir Temur.

From the Tsar and the Master Temurbek to the cities and lands of Castile and the King of Spain

Text

This deed was written on May 15, 1402, and we have affixed our seal to it in order to be authentic. [2;18.]

The historical appearance of documents is made up of parts such as who the document is from, in whose name it is, text, seal, date. These are considered essential parts of documents, and these parts were used in each document. The components of the document have their own functions, they express who the document is from and to whom, and the seal part ensures the reliability of the document, while the date part indicates when the document was signed, which also plays an important role in documentation. These parts have been preserved in today's documents. For example, we give the text of the application that is widely used among the people today:

Chinoz district, Tashkent region

To the head physician of Hospital No. 4, S.R.Rakhimov
attending physician Karima Batyrovna

From Sobirovna

APPLICATION

I would like to ask you to hire me as a doctor in the internal medicine department of Hospital No. 4.

The necessary documents were attached to the application.

2000.10.02. (Signature) K.Sobirova

Along with this, a number of necessary parts were added and have become the present-day form and are called necessary parts of documents or requisites. [1;21.] These necessary parts in documents have a strict order of arrangement. Certain requisites must be present in each document. Their absence deprives the document of legal force. Similarly, some requisites are used where one

is used, the other is not. The fact that the necessary parts of a document are subject to the general rules of document preparation and have a stable arrangement helps in the preparation of printed business papers - ready-made forms. This, in turn, ensures that we achieve positive results in business and creates convenience.

In general, the history of the formation of document requisites that are practically used in the life of our society today dates back to the distant past, and although the necessary parts of the document have undergone some changes, they have retained the basic structure used in the past.

REFERENCES

1. Aminov A., Madvaliyev A., Mahkamov N., Mahmudov N. Business administration. – Tashkent, 2002. - P. 21.
2. Kholbekov M. Correspondence of Amir Temur with European Kings. Samarkand, 1996.
3. Omonov K. Linguistic and methodological study of state documents granting the right to privileges written in Uyghur script in the 14th-15th centuries. Philology. Candidate of Sciences. Dissertation. – Tashkent, 1997.
4. Sodiqov Q. Old Uyghur writing. – Tashkent, 1989.